

Synthesis of Aryl Ketone-(4-Aryl-2-Thiazolyl)-Hydrazones

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A course of reaction between ω -bromo-aryl ketones and thiosemicarbazones has been investigated.

A study of Hantzsch-type synthesis with thiosemicarbazide and aliphatic α -halo carbonyl compounds has revealed a variety of products the nature of which depends on the structure of the reactants and particularly on the reaction conditions¹. Substituted thiosemicarbazides and α -halo carbonyl compounds give 2-hydrazino derivatives of thiazoles².

We have investigated reaction course between various thiosemicarbazones (I) and ω -bromo aryl ketones (II). The products obtained are aryl ketone-(4-aryl-2-thiazolyl)-hydrazones (III) which were confirmed by an alternative synthetic route following Beyer².

R = Ph, *p*-Cl.C₆H₄, *p*-Br.C₆H₄, *p*-CH₃.C₆H₄, *p*-CH₃O.C₆H₄, 2-C₁₀H₇, 2-thienyl.

R' = Same as R.

These compounds have been characterized by their IR Spectra³: 1600–1550 cm⁻¹ (*m*) (thiazole I); 1460(*s*), 1380(*s*) cm⁻¹ (skeletal vibrations); 1190–1175 cm⁻¹ (skeletal C–C–vibrations); 1050 cm⁻¹ (*m* to *s*) (C–H in plane and ring skeletal vibrations); 860–720 cm⁻¹(*s*) (ring vibrations and C–H out of plane deformations).

These compounds are shown in Table 1.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of acetophenone/acetophenone/acetophenone-(4-substituted aryl/naphthyl/thienyl-2-thiazolyl)-hydrazones: A solution of ω -bromo-acetophenone (0.01M) in 10 ml. methanol was mixed with solution of thiosemicarbazone (0.012M) in 10 ml. methanol and refluxed on a steam-bath for 3 hrs,

TABLE I

Acetophenone/Acetonaphthone/Acetothienone, (4-aryl/naphthyl/thienyl-2-thiazolyl)-hydrazones

Sr. No.	R	R'	M.P. (°C)	Molecular Formula	Analysis %N		Analysis %S	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	137	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ S	14.12	14.32	10.80	10.91
2.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	170	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ S	12.72	12.82	9.80	9.77
3.	"	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ -	175	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ S	11.30	11.29	8.71	8.60
4.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	140	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	13.76	13.68	10.32	10.42
5.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	13.10	13.00	9.80	9.90
6.	"	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	223	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	12.35	12.25	9.42	9.33
7.	"	2-Thienyl	120	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	13.89	13.98	21.32	21.40
8.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	182	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ S	12.72	12.82	9.63	9.77
9.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	187	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃	11.52	11.60	8.75	8.84
10.	"	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ -	205	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrClN ₃ S	10.43	10.33	7.78	7.87
11.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	175	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ S	12.30	12.29	9.40	9.37
12.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	130	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS	11.68	11.82	8.86	8.95
13.	"	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	206	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ S	11.03	11.13	8.39	8.48
14.	"	2-thienyl-	142	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ S ₂	17.89	17.99	19.00	19.19
15.	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	177	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ S	11.31	11.29	8.60	8.60
16.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	190-5	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrClN ₃ S	10.33	10.33	7.78	7.87
17.	"	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ -	175	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Br ₂ N ₃ S	9.21	9.31	7.10	7.09
18.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	130	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ S	10.78	10.87	8.30	8.29
19.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	140	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ OS	10.60	10.45	7.89	7.96
20.	"	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ S	9.84	9.95	7.69	7.58
21.	"	2-Thienyl-	135	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ S ₂	11.12	11.11	16.99	16.93
22.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	205	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	13.69	13.68	10.32	10.42
23.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	163	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ S	12.19	12.29	9.20	9.27
24.	"	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ -	198	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ S	10.78	10.87	8.30	8.29
25.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	163	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ S	13.08	13.08	9.87	9.97
26.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	122	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	12.50	12.47	9.47	9.60
27.	"	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	221	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ S	11.67	11.76	8.86	8.96
28.	"	2-Thienyl-	115	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂	13.33	13.42	20.40	20.44
29.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	12.85	13.00	10.01	9.91
30.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	150	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS	11.72	11.82	8.90	8.95
31.	"	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ -	125	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ OS	10.35	10.45	7.95	7.96
32.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	120	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	12.56	12.49	9.41	9.50
33.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	105	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	11.86	11.96	9.10	9.06
34.	"	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	205	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	11.10	11.26	8.20	8.23
35.	"	2-Thienyl-	90	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ OS ₂	12.67	12.76	19.54	19.45
36.	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	106	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	12.16	12.25	9.22	9.33
37.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	182-3	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ S	11.21	11.13	8.47	8.48
38.	"	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ -	185	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ S	9.95	9.95	7.61	7.58
39.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	125	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ S	11.75	11.76	8.87	8.96
40.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	154	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	11.08	11.26	8.32	8.23
41.	"	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	200	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ S	10.65	10.69	8.15	8.14
42.	"	2-Thienyl-	150	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	12.05	12.03	18.34	18.33
43.	2-Thienyl-	C ₆ H ₅ -	132	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	14.00	13.98	21.31	21.40
44.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	90	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClN ₃ S ₂	17.88	17.99	19.00	19.19
45.	"	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄ -	95	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ BrN ₃ S ₂	11.01	11.11	16.92	16.93
46.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	13.33	13.42	22.34	22.44
47.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ -	100	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS ₂	12.67	12.76	19.50	19.45
48.	"	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	174	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	12.01	12.03	18.23	18.33
49.	"	2-Thienyl-	75	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	13.67	13.77	31.36	31.47

After reaction was over, the reaction mixture was treated with a few drops of dilute NH_3 till basic to litmus paper. It was again warmed and filtered while hot and the solvent was allowed to evaporate. The residue obtained was crystallized either from methanol or from petrol ether. The overall yield of the products was between 60 to 70%.

R E F E R E N C E S

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